

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

HYDROCHEMICAL ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY IN SMALL LAKES IN THE NATIONAL PARK «VALDAISKY»

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of water quality in some small lakes of the Valdaisky National Park. As to the results of the research, the water pollution index was calculated, based on which the water of lakes Sominets, Pavlovo and Ukleinskoye, according to the standards in force in the Russian Federation, can be characterized as clean, and the water of Lake Mokhovoe - as moderately polluted.

Keywords: hydrochemical studies, water quality, pollution index, small lakes, Valdaisky National Park.

The Valdaisky National Park is one of the most significant environmental research centers in the European part of Russia. Programs aimed at environmental education and the development of ecological tourism are successfully implemented on its' territory. However, the main task of the park is to preserve the unique natural complex of the Valdai Upland. Since the foundation of the park in 1990, there have been conducted various biological and ecological studies with the participation of the scientific department of the park. During them, particular attention is paid to the water resources of the park. The water system of the park is its main part: the rivers and lakes have rich ityofauna, there are such valuable fish species as peled, smelt, carp, and others. In addition, water bodies play an important role in the life of many other representatives of the flora and fauna here, including a number of species listed in the Red Book of the Russian Federation [4].

More than 270 lakes are located within the boundaries of the Valdaisky Park, of which 56 have an area of more than 20 hectares. The largest lakes are Borovno, Valdai, Dinner, Velyo, and Seliger. However, the vast majority of the park's lakes are classified as small lakes. At the same time, a significant part of them are located in the recreational and buffer zones of the park and experience a significant anthropogenic load. Thus, one of the main activities of the Valdai Park is the environmental monitoring of small and medium-sized water bodies, and the solution of problems associated with their ecological state [4].

The level of pollution of the lakes of the park is affected with the development of the shores of reservoirs, including unauthorized ones, the ingress of untreated and undertreated domestic wastewater into reservoirs, recreational load, and other factors [2].

The purpose of this work is to assess the water quality of some small lakes in the park that are experiencing anthropogenic pressure of varying degrees of intensity. The quality of waters should be monitored not only to maintain species diversity and sustainability of the ecosystem, but also to understand the possibility of using those waters for the sake of ecological tourism, which is one of the main activities of the park. It is also

worth emphasizing that small water system are the subjected to anthropogenic influence, so their ecosystems are most sensitive to various kinds of pollution [2].

The study was conducted by SPbSUVM in June 2022 on the basis of the laboratory and with the assistance of the scientific department of NP Valdaisky. The following lakes with a mirror area of up to 10 km², located in the park, were chosen as objects of the study: lakes Pavlovo, Mokhovoe, Ukleinskoe and Sominets. The choice of objects for the study is determined by their location: lakes Ukleinskoe and Pavlovo belong to the system of Lake Velyo, one of the largest and economically significant lakes in the park. In addition, settlements or recreational or economic activities are located on the shores of all the lakes.

Hydrological observation posts and sampling sites were established in accordance with RD 52.24.309–2016. The main hydrochemical indicators (dissolved oxygen concentration, biochemical oxygen consumption, concentration of nitrates, nitrites, ammonium, iron and phosphate ions) provided for by the environmental monitoring program were determined. Based on the results, the water pollution index and the water quality class were calculated [8].

Since amateur fishing is carried out on all lakes [1], the criteria for the quality of their water are the maximum permissible concentrations approved by orders of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation No. 552, No. 454 and No. 116.

At the time of the work in all the studied reservoirs, the maximum permissible concentrations of nitrates, nitrites, ammonium ions, phosphates and iron ions were not exceeded. However, the content of oxygen dissolved in water was unfavorable for the development of most aquatic organisms. The oxygen concentration in the waters of lakes Sominets, Pavlovo and Mokhovoe was 6 mg/l, which, according to the standards adopted in the Russian Federation, is the lowest limit. For Lake Ukleinskoe, the oxygen concentration was 7.5 mg/L [7]. The decrease in the oxygen content in summer in lakes Sominets, Pavlovo and Mokhovoe, as well as in Lake Velyo, is apparently associated with

the massive development of phytoplankton and significant heating of water masses (up to 22°C and above), and appear to be seasonal [5].

Based on the data obtained, a water pollution index (WPI) was calculated for each lake. The calculation results are shown in the graph below.

Water Pollution Index

In accordance with GOST R 58556-2019, waters with a pollution index from 0.2 to 1.0 belong to the II class of quality and are assessed as clean, and waters with a quality index from 1.0 to 2.0 belong to the III class quality, and are rated as moderately polluted.

Thus, based on the conducted reconnaissance studies, the waters of Sominets, Pavlovo and Ukleinskoye lakes belong to the II class of water quality (clean), and the water of Lake Mokhovoe belongs to the III class of quality (moderately polluted). According to GOST R 58556-2019, such lakes are characterized by a threshold vulnerable state of the ecosystem [3].

Lakes Pavlovo, Ukleinskoe, Mokhovoe and Sominets are located in the buffer zone of the Valdaisky National Park and, therefore, are subject to anthropogenic pressure. According to the data obtained earlier, the water of a number of small lakes in the buffer zone of the park (Vasilkovo, Gniskoye, Zaluzhsky lakes), on the banks of which agricultural and household work is traditionally performed also belong to the III class of water quality. Based on this, it can be assumed that the small lakes of the park are highly sensitive to anthropogenic pollution [6], however the ecosystem of those water bodies is still capable of coping with pollution by allochthonous organic matter. What is well illustrated by long-term studies on the waters of Lake Velyo, the system of which includes the Pavlovo and Ukleinskoye lakes. The water of this lake is assessed as a whole as clean-moderately polluted, and only in the area of the residential zone and fishery areas as polluted [5]. A similar situation is observed on the Zaluzhsky lakes. A number of small lakes of this lake system, located on agricultural land and used in agricultural production, have a lower water quality than the lakes of the system that are difficult to access and practically not used by humans. The former are characterized as moderately polluted, and the latter as clean. It should be noted that the unnormalized load on the lakes from the enterprises

of the agro-industrial complex, the absence or low quality of treatment facilities in residential areas, and sometimes ignoring environmental requirements on the part of the population will inevitably lead to a deterioration in water quality in the foreseeable future. National Park "Valdaisky" actively attracts researchers to monitor the state of lake hydro-ecosystems, conducts control, explanatory and environmental activities. However, the efforts of the administration and employees of the NP "Valdaisky" alone might not be enough to prevent the deterioration of water quality in the lakes, the participation of village administrations and the local population in these activities is necessary. Studies of the waters of the small lakes Ukleinskoye, Mokhovoe, Sominets and Pavlovo, conducted in 2022, are reconnaissance, for a more accurate assessment of the ecological state and development of a program for the rehabilitation of these small reservoirs on the territory of the Valdaisky National Park, further detailed hydrochemical and hydrobiological studies are required.

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ФИЗИОЛОГО-БИОХИМИЧЕСКИЕ СВОЙСТВА И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ КЛУБЕНЬКОВЫХ БАКТЕРИЙ *RHIZOBIUM GALEGAE* В ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ

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Аннотация

Физиолого-биохимические свойства микроорганизмов играют определяющую роль при отборе наиболее активных штаммов для использования их в сельскохозяйственном и промышленном производстве и восстановления загрязненных объектов окружающей среды. Изучены физиолого-биохимические свойства штаммов клубеньковых бактерий *Rhizobium galegae*: способность штаммов клубеньковых бактерий к синтезу экзополисахаридов и β-ИУК, термоустойчивость, толерантность к углеводородам нефти, способность использовать нефть в качестве единственного источника углерода, солеустойчивость, а также изучено влияние инокуляции семян клубеньковых бактерий *R. galegae* на синтез растительных белков. Отобраны наиболее перспективные штаммы *R. galegae*, обладающие спектром физиолого-биохимических свойств, обеспечивающих устойчивость и активность функционирования в экстремальных условиях. Установлено, что штаммы клубеньковых бактерий *R. galegae* в ассоциации с растением-хозяином *Galega orientalis* Lam. способствуют увеличению экспрессии белка, способствуют ускорению синтеза полипептидов с молекулярной массой 56,0кД и 12,0кДРБФКО.

Abstract

Physiological and biochemical properties of microorganisms play a decisive role in the selection of the most active strains for their use in agricultural and industrial production and restoration of polluted environmental sites. Physiological and biochemical properties of *Rhizobium galegae* strains were studied: ability of rhizobia strains to synthesize exopolysaccharides and β-IUC, thermal stability, tolerance to oil hydrocarbons, ability to use oil as a single source of carbon, salt tolerance, and the effect of *R. galegae* seed inoculation on plant proteins synthesis was studied. The most promising strains of *R. galegae* possessing a spectrum of physiological and biochemical properties providing stability and activity of functioning under extreme conditions have been selected. It was found